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An Atlas of astronaut photographs of Earth at Night

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Astronauts have been taking photos of Earth for decades_(Pettit 2008), but the last few years have seen a dramatic increase in the quality of the imagery, particularly at night. Nighttime images often have a large public resonance, perhaps because artificial light at night is such a unique signature of human activity on Earth (see e.g. Figure 1). While these beautiful pictures are freely available from a NASA repository ([The Gateway to Astronaut Photography of Earth](#)), the sheer number of photos can make finding, for example, an image of a particular city at night a challenge. In many cases, considerable time must be invested in order to find the original data for an image popularised by an astronaut through twitter.

The illumination observed at night comes primarily from outdoor area lighting (e.g. street lighting, see Kuechly et al, 2012) and architectural lighting. Astronaut photographs have several major advantages over satellite observations from sensors like the well known DMSP/OLS or the new VIIRS Day Night Band (see Miller et al. 2013). Such photographs offer far better spatial resolution (better than 10 meters compared to 750 meters), three spectral bands in the visible range (compared to one which includes sensitivity to some_infrared but not blue light), and variable overpass times (as opposed to fixed). If the thousands of images were more easily available, they could surely be of great use in many disparate fields, including for example human geography, ecology and conservation biology, energy and carbon analysis and policy, public safety, epidemiology of light at night mediated disease, and our personal research topic: improving understanding of light pollution.

To facilitate our own research (Zamorano, et. al. 2011), over the last three years we have compiled an Atlas of astronaut images of the Earth at night. The Atlas was manually compiled by inspecting over 300,000 images from The Gateway to Astronaut Photography of Earth, and comparing selected images to DMSP/OLS data and online maps (Google maps, Open street maps, etc). The Atlas currently has 1695 nighttime images of known cities. Besides making finding images of particular cities far easier, the Atlas includes additional information not available in the NASA gateway, for example the image ISO and exposure time. The Atlas has now developed to the point that we feel it can be of major use to other researchers, as well as to journalists, policy makers, and interested citizens.

We have developed a web portal to allow easy access to the images. Figure 2 shows a map of the Earth, with dots showing cities for which we have a tagged photograph. Clicking on any of the dots will bring up a box containing detailed information about the photograph, including a thumbnail and a link to the original raw image at the NASA website. The Atlas also provides a link to an interactive table that allows the user to apply filters to find relevant images (e.g. searching for a specific city, latitude and longitude, or time of night). It is our hope that making such images more widely available will lead to better understanding and conservation of the Earth's night.

These pictures were made possible because of public funding for space exploration. Moving forward, we intend to use these images to involve the public more directly in research. In addition to the Atlas, we have developed an online portal to allow citizen scientists to aid in classification of all of the nighttime images ever taken from the International Space Station. Our initial atlas contains photographs from hundreds of cities worldwide, but we know that there are many more images still hidden in the dark of the repository. The astronauts also continue to take new photographs that will also need classification. In addition to helping improve our understanding of Earth, we hope that participation in this project will be rewarding to the participants (e.g. pride at finding and publicizing an image of their hometown). We have also developed a tool that allows interested citizen scientists to further apply their lay knowledge, by georeferencing images using maps of the cities that they are familiar with.

We want to thank to the Astronauts that have taken the pictures, and in particular astronauts Sochi, Haldfield, Kupiers, Pettit, and Parmitano. We also acknowledge the international cooperation that makes the International Space Station and this research possible.

Our motivation for working on characterisation of the images was to make use of them as a scientific tool. But we hope that our Atlas will be an example of the achievements that are possible when we work together, and a demonstration of the value that open data policies provide to the citizens of Earth. We invite you to visit www.citiesatnight.org to browse images or to become a contributor.

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Figure 1: Shanghai city center from the ISS. Image ISS034-E-38784. Cortesy “The Gateway to Astronaut Photography of Earth”

Figure 2. Screenshot of the main Atlas webpage (www.citiesatnight.org). The Atlas makes use of a Google maps interface, allowing users bring up photographs of a given city simply by clicking on the dot.